

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

*ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal*

2026-YIL
IYUN/6-SON, IV-QISM

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 - Texnika fanlari

08.00.00 - Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google
Scholar

ISSN INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD
SERIAL
NUMBER
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

OpenAIRE

ISSN: 3060-463X

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 2026-yil, iyun.

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afrovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Mahammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

Yusupov Maxamadamin Abduxamidovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor

Kalonova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor.

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Norboyev Odil Abrayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Pardaev Umidjon Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc)

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
05.08.06 – "G'ildirakli va gusenisali mashinalar va ularni ishlatish" (texnika fanlari)
05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
08.00.11 – Marketing
08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
08.00.13 – Menejment
08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

EPOKSID-DIAN VA FENOLFORMALDEGID GIBRID BOG'LOVCHISI ASOSIDA YUQORI YEYILISH VA KORROZIYABARDOSH ANTIFRIKSION QOPLAMALAR YARATISH	10
Bakirov Lutfillo Yuldoshaliyevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIKNI BOSHQARISH VA TARTIBGA SOLISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI.....	16
Mamayusupova Dilovarxon, Maxmudaliyeva Manzuraxon, Toyirjonov Shokirjon	
FRANSUZ, RUS VA O'ZBEK TILLARI SPORT TURIZMI TERMINLARINING LEKSIK-SEMANTIK VA LINGVOMADANIY TADQIQI.....	20
Ma'rupova Gulnoz	
МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ОЦЕНКЕ ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ХРАНЕНИЯ ПЛОДОВ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	24
Муратов Абдулазиз Уктамович	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND EMERGING TRENDS IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY.....	29
Daminova Barno, Esmurodova Zarnigor, Boltayev Javohir, Kuziboyeva Lobar	
FRANSUZ, RUS VA O'ZBEK TILLARI SPORT TURIZMI TERMINLARINING LEKSIK-SEMANTIK VA LINGVOMADANIY XUSUSIYATLARI.....	34
Ma'rupova Gulnoz Umarjonovna	
MINTAQA IQTISODIY O'SISHIDA XIZMATLAR SOHASI TARKIBIY O'ZGARISHLARINING STATISTIK TAHLILI: XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA	38
Raximov Alisher Ibragimovich	
KREDIT SKORINGIDA XULQ-ATVOR OMILLARINI BAHOLASH: NAZARIY ASOSLAR VA AMALIY QO'LLANILISHI	45
BekmurodovAbbos Amiriddinovich	
ECONOMETRIC INVESTIGATION OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION ACTIVITIES IN KARAKALPAKSTAN REPUBLIC.....	49
Makhambetova Uringul Reimbaevna	
GETEROKOMPOZIT POLIMER QOPLAMALAR SIRTINING SHAKLLANISHI VA ULARNING PAXTA TOLALARI SIFATIGA TA'SIRINI TADQIQ ETISH	55
Bakirov Lutfillo Yuldoshaliyevich	
GRADIENT BOOSTING (XGBOOST) VA TEGISHLILIK FUNKSIYALARIGA TAYANGAN STATISTIK KLASSIFIKATSIYA USULINING SOLISHTIRMA BAHOLANISHI	62
Ergasheva Ma'mura Gayratovna	
QURILISH SOHASIDA KICHIK VA YIRIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI INTEGRATSIYASI SAMARADORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK BAHOLASH.....	69
Axmedova Nilufar Shuxratovna	
LARAVEL PLATFORMASIDA NEYROTARMOQLARNI QO'LLASH ORQALI FOYDALANUVCHI XATTI-HARAKATLARINI BASHORAT QILISH VA TAVSIYA TIZIMLARINI YARATISH	74
Jo'rayev To'xtasin, Abdusattarov Odiljon, Boymatov Mexrojiddin, Maxkamov A'zimjon, Nabijonov Abduqodir	
BEHIND THE 30% TARGET: A CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK FOR WOMEN'S ACADEMIC LEADERSHIP IN UZBEK UNIVERSITIES	82
Farida Nishanova	
QURILISH SANOATIDA TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLAR VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR	87
Abdullayev Axror Jaxbarovich	
BALIQCILIKDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING OBYEKTIV ZARURIYATI.....	92
Iskandar Yunusov	

TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI KREDITLASHDAGI BANK KREDIT RISKLARINI PASAYTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	98
Toymuxamedov Ibrohim Rixsiboyevich	
KO'P KVARTIRALI UY-JOY FONDINI BOSHQARISHDA PROFESSIONAL XIZMAT KO'RSATISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARI	108
Rahimov Qodir Ergashevich	
НИЗКОУГЛЕРОДНАЯ ЭНЕРГЕТИКА КАК НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	115
Расулкулов Жамшидбек Акрамкулович	
ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONALARNING MOHIYATI VA ULARNING PRINSIPLARI	124
Ubaydullayev Muxammadjon, Akbarov Diyorbek	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA MEHMONXONA XIZMATLARINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISHNING IQTISODIY AFZALLIKLARI.....	128
Raxmonova Nigina Anvarovna	
EMPLOYEE WELL-BEING IN POST-REFORM UZBEKISTAN: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW AND RESEARCH AGENDA	132
Farida Nishanova	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI MOLIALASHTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	137
Inobatov Abror Boshlarovich	
REAL SEKTORNING INSTITUTSIONAL TARKIBI VA TRANSFORMATSIYA TENDENSIYALARI.....	144
Isroilova Muhabbat Rustamjon qizi	
ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ РОСТА ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ФИРМЕННЫХ МАГАЗИНОВ «SAG EXPRESS»)	151
Мусаева Шоира Азимовна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YALPI ICHKI MAHSULOT DINAMIKASINING ICHKI ISTE'MOLGA TA'SIRI	161
Djumayev Zayniddin Axmedovich	
O'ZBEKISTON TASHQI IQTISODIY FAOLIYATIDA KICHIK BIZNES O'RNINI OSHIRISHNING STATISTIK USULLARDAGI TAHLILI.....	166
Yadgarova Nigora Rixsulla qizi	
KATTA HAJMDAGI MA'LUMOTLARNI REAL VAQT REJIMIDA VIZUALIZATSIYA QILISH UCHUN ADAPTIVE M4 GEOMETRIK-PERSEPTUAL AGREGATSIYA ALGORITMI.....	170
Nuraliyev Faxriddin, Hotamov Farhod, Muxamedjonova Zuxra	
АЛГОРИТМ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ ПРОПУСКНОЙ СПОСОБНОСТИ В РАЗВЕТВЛЁННЫХ ПАССИВНЫХ ОПТИЧЕСКИХ СЕТЯХ (PON).....	175
Киямов Рахматулло Рузиевич	
MARKETING KOMMUNIKATSIYALARI ORQALI HUDUDLARNING INVESTITSION SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH.....	180
Xolmurotova Diyoraxon, Xoliyorova Shoxista	
OZIQ-OVQAT XAVSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA DAVLAT STRATEGIK ZAXIRALARINING O'RNINI	184
Bazarov Nazirjon, Normurodov Alibek	
O'ZBEKISTONDA KAMBAG'ALLIKNI QISQARTIRISH VA UNI BARTARAF ETISHDA TADBIRKORLIKNING ROLI: IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA TENDENSIYALAR.....	190
Uzakov Sh. Sh.	
MINTAQADA TABIIY KAPITALNI JAMG'ARISHNING TASHKILY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH (XORAZM VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	196
Raximov Faxriddin Shavkatovich	
СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ УГРОЗЫ ФИНАНСОВОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ СТРАХОВЫХ КОМПАНИЙ И ПРИЧИНЫ ИХ ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЯ	201
Петр Ким	

УЧЁТ ВЫБЫТИЯ ОСНОВНЫХ СРЕДСТВ И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА ФИНАНСОВЫЕ РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ.....	207
Туракулов Шахриёр, Пашаходжаева Дилдора HUDUDIY IQTISODIY O‘SISH DRAYVERLARINI KO‘P OMILLI REGRESSION TAHLIL ASOSIDA MIQDORIY BAHOLASH (BUXORO VILOYATI TUMANLARI MISOLIDA).....	213
Ergashev Sherali Erali o‘g‘li NOAN‘ANAVIY PUL-KREDIT SIYOSATI INSTRUMENTLARINING MAKROIQTISODIY KO‘RSATKICHLARGA QISQA MUDDATLI TA‘SIRINI EMPIRIK BAHOLASH	217
Djumonov Dilshod Safaroliyevich O‘ZBEKISTONDA YALPI ICHKI MAHSULOT DINAMIKASINING ICHKI ISTE‘MOLGA TA‘SIRI	222
Djumayev Zayniddin Axmedovich JIZZAX VILOYATI KICHIK BIZNES TIZIMINING EMPIRIK MA‘LUMOTLAR BAZASI VA TAVSIFIY STATISTIK TAHLILI	227
Atamuratova Gulrux Muzafarovna KIMYO SANOATI KORXONALARIDA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA SAMARADORLIGINI INTEGRAL BAHOLASH VA 2032-YILGACHA PROGNOZLASH.....	232
Razikov Otabek Rustamovich ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПАРАМЕТРОВ РАЗВОЛКНЕНИЯ ПУТАНКИ	240
Одилхонова Нафиса, Атаханов Авазбек SOLIQ BOSHQARMALARIDA AGILE MENEJMENT TAMOYILLARIDAN FOYDALANISH ISTIQBOLLARINING EMPIRIK-STATISTIK TAHLILI	247
Sayfiyev Jasur Ravshanovich O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA DAVLAT XARIDLARI TIZIMIDA RAQOBAT MUHITI VA SHAFFOFLIKNI TA‘MINLASHNING MOLIYAVIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	253
Rizoqulova Elnora Otabek qizi YOSHLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING MINTAQAVIY OMILLARI.....	260
Ergashev Erkin Iroqovich QULOQ CHANOG‘I VA YUZ YON TASVIRI ASOSIDA SHAXSNI IDENTIFIKATSIYALASH.....	264
Mamatov Narzillo, Samijonov Abdurashid, Abdullaeva Barno, Usarov Jurabek ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ РОТОРНО-УПРАВЛЯЕМЫХ СИСТЕМ (РУС) И ВИНТОВЫХ ЗАБОЙНЫХ ДВИГАТЕЛЕЙ (ВЗД) ПРИ БУРЕНИИ НЕФТЯНЫХ И ГАЗОВЫХ	271
Жахонгир Эркин угли Абдиганиев, Шерали Халлокович Умедов KO‘KRAK BEZI SARATONINING MOLEKULYAR SUBTIPLARINI PROGNOZ QILISHDA MULTIPARAMETRIK MRT VA SUN‘IY INTELLEKT MODELLARINING INTEGRATSIYASI	282
Sulaymanov Dilshod, Alikariyev Isroiljon ERKIN IQTISODIY HUDUDLAR VA KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARINI TASHKIL ETISH HAMDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH (“URGUT” ERKIN IQTISODIY ZONASI MISOLIDA)	288
Yazdanov Mirjaxon G‘ayrat o‘g‘li IQLIM O‘ZGARISHLARINING HUDUD BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHIGA TA‘SIRINI BAHOLASH REYTINGI: NAZARIY-USLUBIY YONDASHUV	294
Madenova Elmira Nizamatdinovna TIJORAT BANKLARI FOYDASINI SOLIQQA TORTISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	300
Turanov M. Sh. BELAZ YUK MASHINALARINING SHARLI O‘Q DETALLARDAGI KUCHLANISH KONSENTRATSIYASINING TAHLILI VA MUSTANKAMLIKKA TA‘SIRI.....	306
Yusupov Abdulaziz, Pushanov Akbar, Jo‘raqulov Ixtiyor, Jaxonov Shoxrux ОЧИСТИТЕЛЬНАЯ СЕКЦИЯ ХЛОПКООЧИСТИТЕЛЬНОГО АГРЕГАТА С НАКЛОННЫМИ КОЛКАМИ НА КОЛКОВЫХ БАРАБАНАХ.....	311
Эргашев Рахимжон, Мавлянов Айбек, Росулов Рузимурод SUV-SUV TIZIMIDA ISSIQLIK ALMASHINISH JARAYONINI JADALLASHTIRISH	316
Karabayev Asatilla, Yo‘lliyev Shukurali, Abduqayumov Jamoliddin	

HUDUDLARDA AGROTURISTIK SALOHİYATNI BAHOLASH USLUBI	323
Qodirov Azizjon, Rustamov Adhamjon, Jumayeva Ozoda	
ROI-WEIGHTED PRIMARY FRAME FILTERING FOR EFFICIENT DEEP VIDEO SURVEILLANCE	329
Shohruh Begmatov, Mukhriddin Arabboev, Akhram Nishanov	

ROI-WEIGHTED PRIMARY FRAME FILTERING FOR EFFICIENT DEEP VIDEO SURVEILLANCE

Shohruh Begmatov

Tashkent University of Information
Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences
ORCID: 0000-0002-2441-916X

Mukhriddin Arabboev

Tashkent University of Information
Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences
ORCID: 0000-0001-5733-5889

Akhram Nishanov

Tashkent University of Information
Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi
Doctor of Science in Technical Sciences, Professor
ORCID: 0000-0002-5652-8977

Abstract. Real-time video surveillance systems frequently rely on deep neural detectors and multi-object trackers. Although these models provide high detection and tracking quality, processing every frame is computationally expensive, especially for long-term multi-camera deployments. This paper presents an ROI-weighted primary filtering algorithm that decides whether an incoming video frame should be processed by a full deep model or skipped and propagated using previously computed results. The method is motivated by the observation that ordinary mean absolute frame difference treats all pixels equally. At the same time, surveillance decisions are usually more sensitive to changes in object regions than to background fluctuations. The proposed estimator constructs a spatial importance map from previously detected bounding boxes, expands these regions by a dilation margin, and computes a normalized weighted frame-difference score. A cost-minimization rule converts this score into a binary processing gate. Experiments on MOT20 sequences show that the ROI-weighted score amplifies object-related changes by 1.15x to 1.87x relative to global MAFD. Practical deployment scenarios demonstrate that more than 65% of frames can be handled by lightweight filtering, reducing computational load by 56.69% and 61.31% in two surveillance cases. These findings indicate that object-aware frame filtering is a simple and effective pre-inference mechanism for resource-efficient video analytics.

Keywords: video surveillance; frame skipping; ROI-weighted difference; object-aware filtering; multi-object tracking; edge AI; computational load reduction.

Annotatsiya. Real vaqt rejimida ishlovchi video kuzatuv tizimlari ko'pincha chuqur neyron detektorlar va ko'p obyektli kuzatuv algoritmlariga tayanadi. Ushbu modellar yuqori aniqlikdagi aniqlash va kuzatuv sifatini ta'minlashda, har bir kadri qayta ishlash hisoblash jihatidan qimmatga tushadi, ayniqsa uzoq muddatli ko'p kamerali tizimlarda. Ushbu maqolada kiruvchi video kadri to'liq chuqur model orqali qayta ishlash yoki oldingi natijalarni propagatsiya qilish orqali o'tkazib yuborishni aniqlovchi ROI-og'irlikli birlamchi filtrlash algoritmi taklif etiladi. Usul oddiy o'rtacha absolyut kadr farqi barcha piksellarni teng baholashi, video kuzatuv qarorlari esa odatda fon tebranishlariga qaraganda obyekt hududlaridagi o'zgarishlarga sezgirroq bo'lishi bilan asoslanadi. Taklif etilgan baholagich avval aniqlangan chegaralovchi qutilar asosida fazoviy muhimlik xaritasini tuzadi, ushbu hududlarni dilatatsiya chegarasi yordamida kengaytiradi va normallashtirilgan og'irlikli kadrlar farqi ko'rsatkichini hisoblaydi. Xarajatni minimallashtirish qoidasi ushbu ko'rsatkichni binar qayta ishlash darvozasiga aylantiradi. MOT20 ketma-ketliklarida o'tkazilgan tajribalar ROI-og'irlikli ko'rsatkich global MAFD bilan solishtirganda obyekt bilan bog'liq o'zgarishlarni 1.15 martadan 1.87 martagacha kuchaytirishini ko'rsatdi. Amaliy joriy etish ssenariylari kadrlarning 65% dan ortig'i yengil filtrlash orqali qayta ishlanishi mumkinligini, ikki kuzatuv holatida hisoblash yuklamasi mos ravishda 56.69% va 61.31% ga kamayishini ko'rsatdi. Ushbu natijalar obyektga yo'naltirilgan kadr filtrlash resurs tejamkor video tahlil uchun sodda va samarali oldindan inferensiya mexanizmi ekanligini tasdiqlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: video kuzatuv; kadri o'tkazib yuborish; ROI-og'irlikli farq; obyektga yo'naltirilgan filtrlash; ko'p obyektli kuzatuv; edge AI; hisoblash yuklamasini kamaytirish.

Аннотация. Системы видеонаблюдения, работающие в режиме реального времени, часто опираются на глубокие нейронные детекторы и алгоритмы многообъектного отслеживания. Несмотря на то что такие модели обеспечивают

высокое качество обнаружения и сопровождения объектов, обработка каждого кадра требует значительных вычислительных ресурсов, особенно в долгосрочных многокамерных системах. В данной статье представлен алгоритм первичной фильтрации с ROI-взвешиванием, который определяет, следует ли обрабатывать входящий видеокادر полной глубокой моделью или пропустить его с распространением предыдущих результатов. Метод основан на наблюдении, что обычная средняя абсолютная разность кадров одинаково учитывает все пиксели, тогда как решения в задачах видеонаблюдения обычно более чувствительны к изменениям в областях объектов, чем к фоновым колебаниям. Предложенный оценщик строит карту пространственной значимости на основе ранее обнаруженных ограничивающих рамок, расширяет эти области с использованием поля дилатации и вычисляет нормализованную взвешенную оценку межкадровой разности. Правило минимизации затрат преобразует эту оценку в бинарный шлюз обработки. Эксперименты на последовательностях MOT20 показывают, что ROI-взвешенная оценка усиливает изменения, связанные с объектами, по сравнению с глобальным MAFD в диапазоне от 1.15 до 1.87 раза. Практические сценарии внедрения демонстрируют, что более 65% кадров могут обрабатываться с помощью облегченной фильтрации, снижая вычислительную нагрузку на 56.69% и 61.31% в двух случаях видеонаблюдения. Полученные результаты показывают, что объектно-ориентированная фильтрация кадров является простым и эффективным механизмом предварительного инференса для ресурсоэффективной видеоаналитики.

Ключевые слова: видеонаблюдение; пропуск кадров; ROI-взвешенная разность; объектно-ориентированная фильтрация; многообъектное отслеживание; периферийный искусственный интеллект; снижение вычислительной нагрузки.

INTRODUCTION

Deep learning has become the dominant approach for object detection and tracking in surveillance video, particularly through detector-tracker pipelines and efficient object detectors [1], [2], [4]-[6]. Modern detectors can identify pedestrians and other objects with high precision, but their forward passes remain expensive when applied to every frame of continuous video streams. The problem becomes more severe in multi-camera monitoring, public safety systems, transport terminals, retail analytics, and smart-city infrastructures, where cameras produce millions of frames per day.

A straightforward solution is to skip frames or adaptively avoid unnecessary processing, an idea that is consistent with efficient video analytics and surveillance-oriented adaptive inference research [7], [8]. However, naive skipping can damage tracking continuity and increase missed detections, identity switches, and localization errors. A useful filtering mechanism must therefore answer a practical question before running the deep model: is the current frame visually important enough to justify full neural inference? This study addresses this problem using an object-aware frame-difference score. The system gives greater weight to regions where objects were detected in the previous frame because changes within or near these regions are more likely to influence the surveillance model's output.

The main contributions of this paper are threefold: first, it introduces a normalized ROI-weighted frame-difference estimator for object-aware video filtering; second, it derives the frame-processing threshold from a cost-quality trade-off rather than relying solely on heuristic tuning; and third, it evaluates the method on MOT20 sequences and two practical surveillance scenarios (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Example of consecutive MOT20 surveillance frames used for frame-difference analysis¹

1 Source: Prepared by the authors

LITERATURE REVIEW

Online multi-object tracking systems such as SORT and Deep SORT demonstrate that simple motion models and efficient association can support real-time tracking when detections are reliable [1], [2]. SORT combines Kalman filtering and Hungarian assignment for efficient online association [1], while Deep SORT extends this idea with an appearance embedding for more reliable identity association [2]. These systems show that tracking can be efficient, but their performance still depends on the availability and quality of detector outputs.

Lightweight object detection research has emphasized the need for efficient inference on edge devices [4]-[7]. MobileNetV2 uses inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks to reduce computational cost [4]; EfficientDet scales detector depth, width, and resolution efficiently [5]; and YOLOv4 illustrates the ongoing accuracy-speed trade-off in real-time detection [6]. Edge-oriented human detection studies similarly show that surveillance applications require low latency, small memory footprint, and reduced energy consumption [7].

Classical motion analysis often uses frame differencing, background subtraction, optical flow, or motion energy. The simplest measure, mean absolute frame difference, is computationally attractive because it requires only pixel-wise subtraction and averaging. Its limitation is that all pixels contribute equally. In surveillance video, changes from illumination flicker, shadows, reflections, display screens, or camera noise may dominate a global difference score. Conversely, small but important pedestrian movement may occupy only a small portion of the frame and be diluted by the background. This motivates an ROI-weighted formulation. In contrast to general motion cues, the proposed method uses object-region information from the tracking pipeline, which makes the filtering decision more relevant to surveillance targets [1]-[3] (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Example of detections used as object regions for ROI construction²

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Let the input video stream be represented as a sequence of frames:

$$V = \{I_t\}_{t=1}^T, \quad I_t \in R^{H \times W \times C} \quad (1)$$

A conventional detector-tracker pipeline applies a deep model to every frame and then updates the tracking states. For frames, this leads to a high computational cost because detector inference is repeated times. The goal of primary filtering is to define a binary gate. When , the current frame is processed by the full model. When , the system skips full inference and propagates the previous output using a low-cost operator $P(\cdot)$:

$$Y_t = g_t F(I_t) + (1 - g_t) P(Y_{t-1}) \quad (2)$$

The challenge is that the gate must be computationally much cheaper than the detector while still preserving

² Source: Prepared by the authors

the important changes required for detection and tracking. A global difference score can be expressed using the ordinary mean absolute frame difference (MAFD):

$$d_t^{MAFD} = \frac{1}{HWC} \sum_{x=1}^W \sum_{y=1}^H \sum_{c=1}^C |I_t(x,y,c) - I_{t-1}(x,y,c)| \quad (3)$$

The number of pixels and channels normalizes this score, and it increases when the average pixel-level change between consecutive frames increases. However, MAFD is not object-aware. A background screen, lighting change, or camera noise can increase the score even if the tracked objects remain stable. On the other hand, a subtle displacement of a pedestrian may have a limited influence on the global average if the object occupies only a small image area.

The filtering problem can therefore be stated as follows: construct a fast, normalized score across frames that is sensitive to changes in object regions, robust to background variation, and suitable for conversion into a binary processing decision. The proposed solution uses previous detections to build an ROI-weighted spatial importance map (Table 1).

Table 1. The main notation used in the proposed filtering algorithm³

Symbol	Meaning
	Current video frame at time (t)
	Previous video frame
	Set of object boxes detected in the previous frame
	Bounding-box dilation margin
	Background pixel weight
	Additional object-region weight
	Ordinary global mean absolute frame difference
	Proposed ROI-weighted frame difference
	Frame-processing threshold
	Binary gate: process or skip

The proposed method begins from the detections obtained in the previous processed frame. Let the set of detected boxes be defined as:

$$B_{t-1} = \{b_{t-1}^k\}_{k=1}^K \quad (4)$$

where K is the number of detected objects. Each box is expanded by a margin m in order to include likely object displacement between adjacent frames:

$$b_{t-1}^{k,+} = b_{t-1}^k \oplus m \quad (5)$$

Dilation is important because an object can move slightly between consecutive frames, and the pixels that become important may lie just outside the previous bounding box. A coverage count map is then constructed over the image plane. It counts how many dilated boxes cover each pixel:

$$C_t(i,j) = \sum_{k=1}^K 1[(i,j) \in b_{t-1}^{k,+}] \quad (6)$$

Pixels outside all regions have a count of 0. Pixels within a single object region have a count of 1. Pixels within overlapping regions have counts greater than 1, which is useful in crowded scenes where interactions and occlusions are likely. The spatial importance map assigns a base weight to the background and adds object-region importance in proportion to coverage:

$$W_t(i,j) = \omega_b + \omega_o C_t(i,j) \quad (7)$$

This means that overlaps naturally receive higher weight without requiring a separate heuristic for crowd density. The normalized ROI-weighted frame difference is calculated by multiplying the per-pixel absolute difference by the spatial importance map and dividing by the total weight. The normalization factor makes the score comparable across frames, even when the number of detections changes:

$$Z_{t-1} = \sum_{(i,j) \in \Omega} \omega_{t-1}(i,j) \quad (8)$$

3 Source: Prepared by the authors

The final ROI-weighted difference is:

$$\Delta_t^\omega = \frac{1}{z_{t-1}} \sum_{(i,j) \in \Omega} \omega_{t-1}(i,j) \frac{\|I_t(i,j) - I_{t-1}(i,j)\|_1}{255} \tag{9}$$

The proposed estimator has four important properties. First, it is normalized and comparable across frames. Second, it is object-aware because object regions make a greater contribution. Third, it is more robust to background noise than global MAFD. Fourth, it is computationally lightweight and can be used before deep inference (Figures 3 and 4).

Figure 3. Normalized ROI coverage count map. Brighter regions correspond to object coverage and overlap zones⁴

Figure 4. ROI count overlay on the original surveillance frame⁵

The decision to process or skip a frame should not be treated as an arbitrary thresholding step. In the proposed model, the threshold is determined by a trade-off between computation and the expected degradation in quality. If the frame is processed, the system pays the deep inference cost. If the frame is skipped, the system avoids this cost but incurs a quality penalty for propagating the previous result. Let R_t be the expected propagation risk, and let α be a trade-off coefficient that converts quality loss into the same decision scale as computation.

The system should process a frame when the expected quality loss from skipping is larger than the cost of full processing:

$$C_D < \alpha R_t \tag{10}$$

The risk is estimated from the weighted frame-change score through a calibration function. A simple linear model is sufficient for the basic derivation:

$$R_t = \phi(d_t^{ROI}) = \alpha d_t^{ROI} \tag{11}$$

4 Source: Prepared by the authors
 5 Source: Prepared by the authors

where λ is a calibration coefficient learned from the relationship between frame-change statistics and performance degradation. Substituting the linear risk model into the cost inequality gives:

$$C_D < \lambda \alpha d_t^{ROI} \tag{12}$$

Therefore, the threshold is:

$$\tau = \frac{C_D}{\lambda \alpha} \tag{13}$$

Moreover, the decision rule becomes:

$$g_t = f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & d_t^{ROI} > \tau \\ 0, & d_t^{ROI} \leq \tau \end{cases} \tag{14}$$

For nonlinear calibration, the threshold can be generalized as:

$$\tau = \phi^{-1}\left(\frac{C_D}{\lambda}\right) \tag{15}$$

This interpretation is important because it shows that the gate is not a purely empirical switch. It is linked to the balance between computational cost and the estimated loss in tracking quality. In a low-resource edge camera, the deep-processing cost may be effectively high, increasing the threshold and allowing more skipping. In a safety-critical setting, the quality-loss coefficient may be high, lowering the threshold and encouraging more frequent deep processing (Table 2).

Table 2. ROI-weighted primary filtering algorithm⁶

Step	Operation
1	Read the current frame I_t and the previous frame I_{t-1} .
2	Obtain previous object boxes B_{t-1} .
3	Dilate each box by margin m .
4	Construct the coverage count map C_t and the spatial importance map W_t .
5	Compute the normalization factor Z_t .
6	Compute the ROI-weighted frame difference d_t^{ROI} .
7	If $d_t^{ROI} > \tau$, process the frame using the full deep model.
8	Otherwise, propagate the previous output.
9	Return the gate value g_t and the output Y_t .

Several visualizations clarify how the weighting mechanism behaves. First, object boxes from the previous frame are projected onto the image. The coverage map then converts these boxes into a count map of the same size. After normalization, dense or overlapping regions appear brighter. This representation is useful because it transforms detection information into a dense spatial prior for the next frame.

The coverage map can be converted into a heatmap and blended with the original frame. This overlay shows that the method focuses on pedestrian regions and near-object areas rather than uniformly weighting the entire image. In crowded surveillance, these are precisely the regions where missed movements and identity confusion are most likely to occur.

The weighted difference visualization further demonstrates the advantage over ordinary MAFD. While ordinary MAFD highlights raw pixel changes, ROI-weighted differences increase the contribution of changes within detected regions. Thus, the same physical movement can produce a stronger decision signal when it occurs near objects and a weaker signal when it appears in irrelevant background areas (Figures 5 and 6).

6 Source: Prepared by the authors

Figure 5. Visualization of ordinary and ROI-weighted frame difference on consecutive frames⁷

Figure 6. Example of weighted frame-difference visualization in a pedestrian region⁸

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The empirical analysis uses MOT20 sequences, including MOT20-01, MOT20-02, MOT20-03, and MOT20-05 [3]. MOT20 contains challenging, crowded pedestrian scenes, making it suitable for evaluating whether object-aware weighting can reveal meaningful changes that are diluted by global frame statistics. The experiment compares ordinary MAFD and the proposed ROI-weighted difference on consecutive frames.

The key evaluation quantity is the amplification ratio, defined as the mean ROI-weighted difference divided by the mean ordinary MAFD:

$$A = \frac{\text{mean}(a_t^{ROI})}{\text{mean}(a_t^{MAFD})} \quad (16)$$

A higher amplification value indicates that the ROI-weighted estimator responds more strongly to changes in object-related regions. This does not mean that every higher value is automatically better; rather, it shows that the score is more sensitive to the regions most likely to affect detection and tracking. The decision threshold

⁷ Source: Prepared by the authors

⁸ Source: Prepared by the authors

can then be adjusted according to a desired skip rate or quality target (Table 3).

Table 3. Statistical comparison of ordinary MAFD and ROI-weighted frame-difference values on MOT20 sequences⁹

Sequence	Mean MAFD	Mean ROI-weighted difference	Amplification
MOT20-01	0.01736	0.03029	1.80x
MOT20-02	0.01528	0.02824	1.87x
MOT20-03	0.01378	0.01804	1.34x
MOT20-05	0.01699	0.01942	1.15x

The comparison between MAFD and ROI-weighted difference shows that the proposed method consistently increases the frame-change response in object-related regions. The largest amplification was obtained for MOT20-02, where the mean value increased from 0.01528 to 0.02824, corresponding to 1.87x amplification. MOT20-01 also showed strong amplification of 1.80x. MOT20-03 and MOT20-05 produced smaller but still positive amplification values of 1.34x and 1.15x, respectively(Figure 7).

Figure 7. Visualization of ordinary MAFD (left side) and ROI-weighted (right side)¹⁰

These results suggest that the ROI prior is especially useful when meaningful changes are concentrated in detected object regions. The smaller amplification in MOT20-05 may indicate that its global background and object-region changes are more similar, or that the distribution of objects creates less contrast between ROI and non-ROI areas. This is expected because the ROI weighting benefit depends on scene structure, object density, and motion distribution(Figure 8).

Figure 8. Histogram comparison of ordinary MAFD and ROI-weighted frame-difference values for MOT20-02¹¹

The histograms show that the ROI-weighted estimator shifts the distribution toward larger values. For threshold-based filtering, this shift improves separability between frames with object-region activity and frames with low relevant change. The skip-rate curve over threshold values further supports this interpretation: as the threshold increases, fewer frames exceed it, and more frames are skipped. Therefore, the threshold can be tuned to meet a desired computation budget(Figure 9).

⁹ Source: Prepared by the authors

¹⁰ Source: Prepared by the authors

¹¹ Source: Prepared by the authors

Figure 9. Skip-rate curve and temporal evolution of frame-change metrics for MOT20-02¹²

The practical surveillance evaluation confirms that the proposed primary filter can substantially reduce the load of a deep video analytics pipeline. In Scenario 1, the system processed more than 860,000 frames per day. Of these, 66.5% were skipped after the full deep model processed fast analysis and 33.5%. The deep-processing time was 24.86 ms per frame, while the skip-decision time was only 2.44 ms. The measured average frame time was 10.77 ms, corresponding to a 56.69% reduction in load.

In Scenario 2, the system processed approximately 1,256,000 frames during one observation working day. The skip ratio was 65.89%, and the deep-processing ratio was 33.11%. Deep processing required 25.29 ms, whereas the skip decision required 2.14 ms. The measured average frame time was 9.78 ms, and the load reduction reached 61.31% (Table 4).

Table 4. Frame filtering results in two practical surveillance scenarios¹³

Indicator	Scenario 1	Scenario 2
Frames per day	860,000	1,256,000
Skipped frames	66.5%	65.89%
Deep-processed frames	33.5%	33.11%
Average deep-processing time	24.86 ms	25.29 ms
Skip-decision time	2.44 ms	2.14 ms
Average frame time	10.77 ms	9.78 ms
Load reduction	56.69%	61.31%

The computational complexity also supports the measured performance. Full deep processing is dominated by neural inference. If the detector cost per frame is C_D , then processing T frames requires approximately:

$$O(TD) \tag{17}$$

By contrast, the skip decision requires pixel difference calculation and mask multiplication, which are approximately:

$$O(THW+TK) \tag{18}$$

where H and W are the image height and width, and K is the number of previous detections. Since these operations are simple and vectorizable, the filtering stage is much cheaper than full detector inference.

The average time per frame can be expressed as:

$$t_{avg} = r_p t_D + r_s t_S \tag{19}$$

where r_p is the fraction of deeply processed frames, r_s is the fraction of skipped frames, t_D is the average deep-processing time, and t_S is the skip-decision time.

The load reduction relative to full deep processing can be written as:

$$LR = \left(1 - \frac{t_{avg}}{t_D}\right) \times 100\% \tag{20}$$

12 Source: Prepared by the authors

13 Source: Prepared by the authors

The results demonstrate that the proposed primary filtering algorithm significantly decreases computational load. The system processed only about one-third of the incoming frames, while a lightweight decision mechanism processed more than 65%. This confirms the suitability of the proposed method for long-term surveillance systems and multi-camera video analytics.

The proposed ROI-weighted filtering algorithm is attractive because it uses information already produced by the detector. No additional heavy neural model is required. The previous bounding boxes are transformed into a spatial prior, and the final decision is made using a normalized weighted difference. This design is suitable for edge and long-term surveillance because the expensive detector is called only when a visual change is likely to affect object tracking quality. It is also compatible with detector-tracker systems such as SORT and Deep SORT because it reuses the detector output without adding a second heavy model [1], [2].

The method provides interpretable control. The background and object weights define how strongly the system prioritizes object regions over background regions. The dilation margin controls tolerance to short-term motion around previous boxes. The threshold controls the computation-quality balance. Unlike a black-box learned gate, these parameters can be explained to operators and adjusted according to deployment needs.

The result that the ROI-weighted difference amplifies object-related change by 1.15x to 1.87x is important for crowded surveillance scenes. In a dense scene, a small person-level displacement may occupy a limited region of the image but still have a strong effect on tracking quality. Global MAFD may underestimate such movement, whereas ROI weighting increases its influence on the decision score. At the same time, the method does not fully ignore background variation because the background weight remains positive. This helps preserve sensitivity to new objects entering the scene or unexpected global changes.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Several limitations should be considered. First, the method depends on previous detections. If the detector misses an object, that object may not receive ROI weight in the next frame. Second, sudden object entry from outside existing ROIs can be weak unless the background weight and threshold are chosen carefully. Third, camera motion, strong illumination change, and dense non-object background motion can still affect the difference score. Fourth, the current analysis emphasizes frame-change amplification and computational reduction; future evaluation should also include full tracking metrics under different skip rates.

Future work should uncertainty-aware tracking, adaptive threshold learning, and detector confidence calibration. The threshold can also be learned dynamically from recent frame statistics, scene type, camera position, and deployment constraints. It would also be valuable to evaluate the method using tracking metrics such as MOTA, IDF1, HOTA, identity switches, and missed detections. Another promising direction is to combine ROI-weighted filtering with lightweight neural gating, where the proposed score acts as a first-stage interpretable filter before a more selective learned decision module.

This paper presented an ROI-weighted primary filtering algorithm for efficient deep video surveillance. The approach improves ordinary frame differencing by weighting previously detected object regions and overlapping areas. The threshold rule is derived from a cost-minimization principle, making the frame-processing decision interpretable and tunable. On MOT20 sequences, the proposed estimator amplified object-aware frame-change signals by 1.15x to 1.87x compared with ordinary MAFD. In two practical surveillance scenarios, the system skipped more than 65% of frames and reduced computational load by 56.69% and 61.31%. These results indicate that ROI-weighted frame filtering can serve as an effective pre-inference module for real-time and long-duration surveillance analytics. The results support the broader trend toward efficient, adaptive video analytics for crowded surveillance environments.

REFERENCES

1. A. Bewley, Z. Ge, L. Ott, F. Ramos, and B. Upcroft, "Simple online and real-time tracking," in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, 2016, pp. 3464–3468, doi: 10.1109/ICIP.2016.7533003.
2. N. Wojke, A. Bewley, and D. Paulus, "Simple online and realtime tracking with a deep association metric," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, 2017, pp. 3645–3649, doi: 10.1109/ICIP.2017.8296962.
3. P. Dendorfer, H. Rezatofighi, A. Milan, J. Shi, D. Cremers, I. Reid, S. Roth, K. Schindler, and L. Leal-Taixé, "MOT20: A benchmark for multi object tracking in crowded scenes," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2003.09003*, 2020, doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2003.09003.
4. M. Sandler, A. Howard, M. Zhu, A. Zhmoginov, and L.-C. Chen, "MobileNetV2: Inverted residuals and linear bottlenecks," in *2018 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2018, pp. 4510–4520, doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2018.00474.
5. M. Tan, R. Pang, and Q. V. Le, "EfficientDet: Scalable and efficient object detection," in *2020 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2020, pp. 10781–10790, doi: 10.1109/CVPR42600.2020.01079.
6. A. Bochkovskiy, C.-Y. Wang, and H.-Y. M. Liao, "YOLOv4: Optimal speed and accuracy of object detection," *arXiv*

preprint arXiv:2004.10934, 2020, doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2004.10934.

7. S. Y. Nikouei, Y. Chen, S. Song, R. Xu, B.-Y. Choi, and T. R. Faughnan, "Real-time human detection as an edge service enabled by a lightweight CNN," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on EDGE Computing (EDGE)*, 2018, pp. 125–129.
8. T. Yu, C. Chen, Y. Zhou, and X. Hu, "Improving surveillance object detection with adaptive omni-attention over both inter-frame and intra-frame context," in *Proceedings of the Asian Conference on Computer Vision (ACCV)*, 2022, pp. 2697–2712.

muhandislik

& iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Abdurahmon Qurbonov

2026. № 6

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100